

NORMS MENISCUS

SAP ADDENDUM

Study title	Norm change in MENISCUS
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1 Background

The MENISCUS trial is a cluster-randomised controlled trial in Ugandan secondary schools evaluating a comprehensive menstrual health intervention designed to improve adolescent girls' menstrual health, mental health, and educational outcomes. In addition to addressing physical and informational barriers to menstrual hygiene, the intervention includes a norm-targeting component where peer-selected "leadership groups" (MH Action Group) model and promote positive menstrual practices. Norm targeting activities included using drama skits and puberty education. To investigate the role of social norms and networks in sustaining behavioural change, a dedicated work package has been embedded within MENISCUS using theory-driven, validated tools to measure norm strength, peer influence, and network structure.

This document is an addendum to the trial statistical analysis plan on the effect of the intervention and hence it does not repeat the information included there:

<https://www.isrctn.com/ISRCTN45461276>

2 Hypotheses

The following are the main sub-study hypotheses. All constructs mentioned refer to the privacy norm (the informal rule for which girls in this context should keep private when menstruating)

1. Empirical and normative expectations of the privacy norm do not substantially change (between intervention and control group)
2. Less social punishment reported in intervention group
3. Less expectation of social punishment in intervention group
4. Less acceptability for social punishment in intervention group
5. Cluster level norm strength is higher in the intervention group
6. Network data:

- 6.1 Exploratorily describe what is the layer (network tie type)-specific homophily in the expectation and acceptability of punishment
- 6.2 Higher homophily (across all network ties: closeness, frequency of interaction, liking, sharing secrets) in the expectation and acceptability of punishment in the intervention compared to control group (we expect the fear of judgement network to be different compared to the other network ties)

3 Study Methods

3.1 Trial design, Randomization and Sample size

All details of the original trial can be found: Kansime C, Hytti L, Nelson KA, et al. Menstrual health interventions, schooling, and mental health problems among Ugandan students (MENISCUS): study protocol for a school-based cluster-randomised trial. *Trials* 2022; 23: 759.

No sample size calculations were carried out for the social network hypotheses.

4 STATISTICAL PRINCIPLES

4.1 Confidence intervals and p-values

Please refer to main statistical analysis plan:
<https://www.isrctn.com/ISRCTN45461276>

4.2 Adherence and Protocol deviations

Please refer to statistical analysis plan:
<https://www.isrctn.com/ISRCTN45461276>

5 POPULATION & ELIGIBILITY

Norm analysis population: All male and female participants with endline survey data (participants with UNEB scores but no endline survey data were not included) Please refer to main trial protocol and the statistical analysis plan for details of the endline survey population:

<https://doi.org/10.1186/ISRCTN45461276>

Network analysis population: Network data is based on a sub-sample – half of the schools with the smaller number of students (30 schools); schools were selected if they had less than 60 students. 16 intervention and 14 control schools participated to the network tool. The median number of girls per school was 43. Therefore, the hypotheses which involve the network data will be based on this sub-sample. Baseline characteristics of the schools with network data will be checked to compare intervention and control schools.

Network data analysed is based on the female students network data.

Network data was collected two months prior to the endline survey.

	Population
Social norms hypotheses	All endline survey participants (boys and girls)
Network hypotheses	All endline participants with network data from the subset of schools with fewer students)

6 ANALYSIS

6.1 Outcome definitions

6.1.1 Primary outcomes of the sub-study

The research hypotheses specified above describe the specific outcome they refer to.

Primary outcomes are considered the empirical expectation and acceptability of social punishment. Each of these were measures with two separate questionnaire items at the endline survey. One is binary and based on a vignette style question (See appendix). The one is based on a scenario-based question and answered on a continuous scale (0-10) (See appendix).

6.1.2 Secondary outcomes of the sub-study

Punishment behaviour - this is based on self-reported teasing from boys among girls who menstruated in the last 6 months.

Privacy norm - this is based on two questionnaire items assessing the empirical and normative expectations for being private during menstruation (See appendix).

Norm strength at the school level will combine data on behaviour, empirical, social expectations and punishment) based on a modified definition proposed by Szekely et al -Szekely A, Lipari F, Antonioni A, et al. Evidence from a long-term experiment that collective risks change social norms and promote cooperation. *Nat Commun* 2021; 12: 5452.

6.1.3 ERGM specifications

ERGM (Exponential Random Graph Model) is a statistical framework for cross-sectional data, used to model the structure of networks by examining the relationship between network ties and node-level attributes. It is particularly useful for studying homophily—when nodes with similar attributes (e.g., gender, age, norms.) are more likely to have connections. By including terms like nodematch (for homophily based on attributes) in the model, ERGMs help identify whether the observed network structure deviates from randomness due to the influence of homophily or other structural effects. This makes ERGMs a powerful tool for understanding how network ties are shaped by individual characteristics (Lusher, D., Koskinen, J., & Robins, G.

(Eds.). (2013). Exponential random graph models for social networks: Theory, methods, and applications. Cambridge University Press).

Table 1. Main structural parameters and exogenous covariates included in the models

<p>Edge</p>	<p>This term adds a baseline edge density to the model. It represents the presence or absence of edges in the network. It models the overall tendency of nodes to be connected.</p>
<p>Mutual (reciprocity)</p>	<p>The tendency for relationships to be reciprocal. In other words, it models the presence of mutual ties (i.e., if A -> B, then B -> A).</p>
<p>Gwesp (transitivity)</p>	<p>Modelling triadic closure - the tendency for two nodes to form a tie if they share common neighbors. The decay parameter controls the rate of decrease of this effect as the distance between the nodes in the triad increases. Due to computational complexity that the inclusion of this parameter may cause, this parameter may be fixed.</p>
<p>Nodematch (for categorical variables)/ Abs. difference (for continuous variables)</p>	<p>Models homophily in certain attributes, that is the tendency for nodes to be more likely to form ties with other nodes that have the same value for a certain attribute.</p>
<p>Nodefactor(nodeifactor, nodeofactor)/Nodecov</p>	<p>Models the effect of a node's attribute on the likelihood of forming ties. It allows the model to include different baseline rates of edge formation for different values of the node attribute.</p>

Exogenous covariates included in the model (e.g., nodematch, nodefactor, etc.) will be the expectation of punishment (as continuous variable, and as dichotomous for sensitivity analysis) and the acceptability of punishment.

Additional parameters controlling for indegree and outdegree, as well as edgecovariates may be included, if necessary for improving the goodness of fit.

We will start with using ERGMs for multi-layer networks (Krivitsky, P. N., Koehly, L. M., & Marcum, C. S. (2020). Exponential-family random graph models for multi-layer

networks. *psychometrika*, 85(3), 630-659.) to model the following network ties and their overlap simultaneously: frequency of interactions, close friendship, liking, fear of judgement, sharing secrets. We will model homophily related parameters in the outcomes for each type of tie. However, the activity and popularity related with the outcome will be modeled across all types of ties. Each outcome of interest will be modeled separately (that is, not all outcomes will be modeled within a single model). If there will be issues with the convergence, we will use ERGMs for one type of tie (each modeled separately) by either choosing the least similar network ties to model, or combining six types of ties in a smaller number.

After modelling each network, we will use meta-analysis to get pooled estimates of effects, also moderated by network size and intervention/control group.

The assumption is that the intervention gives an opportunity to people and groups to re-evaluate their expectations. Possibly as edge co-variate family relations will be used but depends on outcome sparsity of data.

6.2 Analysis methods

6.2.1 Individual-level analysis

For hypotheses 1- 5 describe above we will use similar methods described in the main trial Statistical Analysis Plan:

<https://www.isrctn.com/ISRCTN45461276>.

Regression models are used to assess the intervention effect on punishment behaviour, empirical expectation of punishment, acceptability of punishment and the privacy norm empirical and normative expectations. The model will account for school level UNEB scores at baseline and district which are the randomisation stratification characteristics and will account for school clustering using random effects. The same model will also be run for the **cluster level outcome (norm strength)** but without the use of random effects.

For the network data (hypothesis 6):

The main outcomes are expectation and acceptability of punishment measured continuously.

Exponential random graph models (ERGM) for multilayered networks for each school. ERGMs will include basic structural parameters (density, reciprocity, transitivity, etc.), and homophily in outcomes of interest ([Placeholder for the final list of outcomes we are interested in]) for each of the network tie. Furthermore, parameters to account for the dependency between different type of networks ties will be included.

If there are issues with convergence, we will use the Multiple regression quadratic assignment procedure (MRQAP).

Goodness of fit (GOF) of all models will be checked, and if not satisfactory, additional parameters (e.g. degree distribution parameters) will be added based on the outcome of the GOF analysis.

Based on converged ERGM (or MRQAP) models, meta-analysis of network models will be conducted and adjusted for UNEB scores (at school level) and district to account for design characteristics of stratified randomisation.

6.2.2 Descriptive analyses

Descriptive network analyses

- We will describe, at the school level, whether the empirical expectations and acceptability of social punishment will be lower in the intervention schools where students in the in the MH action group are more “central” in the network.
- Describe punishment behaviour of reported teasing by intervention and control groups at network level

6.3 Missing data

Please refer to main trial protocol:

Kansiime C, Hytti L, Nelson KA, et al. Menstrual health interventions, schooling, and mental health problems among Ugandan students (MENISCUS): study protocol for a school-based cluster-randomised trial. *Trials* 2022; 23: 759.

Network hypothesis: Where there are students who participated in the endline survey but not the network survey - we will describe the socio-demographic characteristics of these students compared to the overall endline population (from the 30 targeted schools for the network analyses) to check if there are major differences.

6.4 Statistical software

STATA and R packages: ergm, statnet, sna, network, igraph, ergm.multi, and metafor.

Appendix I - Examples of norm items collected in the survey

Do you think girls in your school **should always keep private** when menstruating?	Privacy norm
We are asking the previous question (about girls keeping private when menstruating) to other people (students and teachers) in your school. Out of 10, how many think girls **should always keep private** when menstruating?	Privacy norm normative expectations
Think about girls in your school. Out of 10, how many girls do you think **actually always keep private** when menstruating? (think of	Privacy norm empirical expectations

the last month)	
<p>Anna (a student in this school) was menstruating and she leaked blood so she had a blood stain showing on her skirt. Anna's classmate (a boy) notices that Anna has a blood stain on her skirt</p> <p>What is her classmate (a boy) likely to do? (Select the most likely)</p>	Social consequences/punishment expectations
How acceptable do you think would it be for her classmate (a boy) to react this way?	Acceptability of punishment
<p>In this situation (Anna has a blood stain on her skirt),</p> <p>**Anna's classmate (a boy)** started to tease her. Out of 10, how many **boys** in your school think it is acceptable (abalenzi bameka abalowooza nti kigwanidde) to **tease** Anna if she has a blood stain?</p>	Acceptability of punishment
Out of 10, how many boys in your school would **actually tease** her in this situation?	Punishment expectations